
Manuscript Acknowledgement No.: SJEBM-40-2020

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To,
Anthony Laurel,
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Manuscript Acknowledgement No.: SJEBM-40-2020
Subject: Acknowledgement

Thank you for sending your valuable article for publication in **(SJEBM: Volume-7: Issue-8, Aug, 2020)**; Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management (SJEBM); ISSN 2348-5302 (Online.) & ISSN 2348-8875 (Print)

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